

PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN NATURAL GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract. This article presents the problems of developing students' competence in natural geography, suggestions and recommendations for their implementation.

Key words: natural geography, competence, web-quest, Blended learning, Flipped classroom.

Today, due to the transition of higher education institutions to the credit-module system, there is a need to improve the forms, methods and tools of teaching subjects, to effectively organize independent education and to introduce new approaches to the development of students' competence in natural geography.

In this regard, the methods of improving the forms, methods and tools of geography teaching in our country, that is, in the continuous education system, the mechanisms of using modern pedagogical technologies in the teaching of geography, the theory and practice of using digital technologies in the teaching of geography, research on the formation of creative ability and practical skills of students in geography M. Abdurakhmonov, S. Kh. Matsaidova, R. T. Gaypova, G. M. Tursupbekova, H. B. Nikadambayeva, F. A. Khamroyeva, A. B. Janzakov, M. A. Tojiboyeva, S. K. Researched by scientists such as Dzumbabayeva, Kh.N. Amonov.

Also, the theory of studying world economic and social geography in the Commonwealth of Independent States, the formation of ecological and economic knowledge of students in the process of studying natural geographical sciences, the technology of organizing scientific research activities of students in the study of geocological problems, universal in school based on geographic modeling methods of formation of educational activities, methods of using statistical methods in teaching geography, mechanisms of preparation of future geography students, improvement of the methodical preparation system of geography students in pedagogical higher educational institutions, teaching geography in the continuous education system research on the theory and practice of using information and communication technologies to increase the effectiveness of teaching N.O. Vereshagina, M.T. Gafurov, A.A. Lobjanidze, T.P. Grushina, N.N. Solodukhina, Sh.B. Tabaldiyeva, S.A. Ivanova, T.V. Konstantinova, Ye It was studied by such

scientists as S. Stepanova, Ye. A. Tamojnyaya, V. A. Shemanayev, T. K. Sherbakova, Ye. A. Istomina, G. Y. Neshepurenko, A. S. Baranov, A. I. Sheinis, M. G. Naderi.

Such studies are presented abroad in the works of scientists such as Isidora Sáez Rosenkranz, Yonsa Tiknaz, Olga Maria de Gouveia Masiel, Hassel David, Surto João, Page Tiani, Christian Beverly J., K. Oda.

In the analysis of the works of the above-mentioned scientists, it became clear that the pedagogical scientific-research works carried out in the field of geography education in our country, the Commonwealth of Independent States and abroad mainly focus on the theory and practice of teaching geography in the educational process, in the teaching of geography. The series is devoted to mechanisms for solving problems. However, in their work, the scientific and theoretical completeness of the development of students' competence in natural geography in higher education institutions was not scientifically substantiated.

At the same time, M.A. Tojiboyeva, M.A. Bakhirna, Ye.A. Gonsharlar have put forward some approaches to the development of students' competence in geography [1, 2, 3], but they are innovative in developing students' competence in natural geography. insufficient attention is paid to the use of pedagogical technologies, including "Blended learning", web-quest, "Flipped classroom" technologies. Therefore, the current research, i.e., improving the use of web-quest, "Blended learning", "Flipped classroom" technologies in the development of students' competence in natural geography, is one of the urgent problems.

According to the analysis of the conducted research, in solving the above-mentioned problem, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: clarification of the pedagogical conditions for the development of students' competence in natural geography; development of new approaches to teaching natural geography; development of mechanisms for the effective use of digital technologies in the teaching of natural geography; improving the technologies of using hypermath tools, web-applications, information educational environments, educational portals and educational websites in the organization of independent education of students in subjects related to natural geography; development of the competence of geography professors-teachers to design lessons using educational environments; to select innovative pedagogical technologies that provide effective results in the teaching of natural geography subjects and to test them.

By overcoming these problems, it is possible to develop students' competence in natural geography. As a result, it will be possible to achieve the training of geography specialists in accordance with the requirements of the time.

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